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UDK: 341.231.14-053.2:501.1

UDK: 342.7-053.2:502.1

UDK: 349.6

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17813281

YOUTH CLIMATE LITIGATION AND THE RIGHT TO A HEALTHY ENVIRONMENT

Youth climate litigation refers to legal actions brought by young people, often minors or young adults, against governments and corporations, arguing that their failure to adequately address climate change violates the fundamental human rights of the present and future generations. These lawsuits assert that, due to climate inaction, an unstable climate system harms youth disproportionately, threatening their rights, such as the right to life, health, culture, and a clean and healthy environment (e.g., *Duarte Agostinho and Others v Portugal*, *Neubauer v. Germany*, *Held v. Montana*). Many cases are based on constitutional rights and human rights conventions (e.g., the European Convention on Human Rights, or the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child). A central theme is the principle of intergenerational equity, emphasizing that the decisions of current generations shall not unfairly and unduly burden the future generations. Plaintiffs argue that children and young people are more vulnerable to the physical and psychological effects of climate change (e.g., extreme heat, resource scarcity, climate anxiety). These cases typically target states for insufficient climate policies (mitigation and adaptation), or large corporations for their contributions to greenhouse gas emissions. Thus, youth climate litigation provides a platform for young people to participate meaningfully in legal and political processes, thus demonstrating their capacity to drive systemic change.

Keywords: children's right to a healthy environment, European Convention on Human Rights, European Court of Human Rights, UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, youth climate litigation.

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KLIMATSKI SPOROVI MLADIH I PRAVO NA ZDRAVU ŽIVOTNU SREDINU

Sporovi mladih u vezi s klimatskim promenama odnose se na pravne postupke koje pokreću mladi, često maloletnici ili mlađi punoletnici, protiv vlada i korporacija, tvrdeći da njihov neuspeh u adekvatnom rešavanju klimatskih promena krši temeljna ljudska prava sadašnjih i budućih generacija. U tužbama se tvrdi da nestabilan klimatski sistem nesrazmerno šteti mladima, zbog neaktivnosti u vezi s klimatskim promenama, ugrožavajući njihova prava, poput prava na život, zdravlje, kulturu, čistu i zdravu životnu sredinu (npr. Duarte Agostinho i drugi protiv Portugala, Neubauer protiv Njemačke, Held protiv Montane). Mnogi slučajevi se temelje na ustavnim pravima i konvencijama o ljudskim pravima (npr. Europska konvencija o ljudskim pravima ili Konvencija UN-a o pravima djeteta). Centralna tema ovih klimatskih sporova mladih je načelo međugeneracijske jednakosti, potkrepljeno argumentom da odluke sadašnjih generacija ne smeju neosnovano opteretiti buduće generacije. Aplikatni tvrde da su deca i mladi osetljiviji na fizičke i psihološke učinke klimatskih promena (npr. ekstremne vrućine, nedostatak resursa, klimatska anksioznost). U ovim sporovima se obično targetiraju države zbog neadekvatnih klimatskih politika (ublažavanje i prilagođavanje) ili velike korporacije zbog njihovog doprinosa emisijama gasova sa efektom staklene bašte. Dakle, klimatski sporovi mladih pružaju platformu mladim ljudima da smisleno učestvuju u pravnim i političkim procesima, čime pokazuju svoj kapacitet za pokretanje sistemskih promena.

Ključne riječi: pravo djece na zdravu životnu sredinu, Europska konvencija o ljudskim pravima, Europski sud za ljudska prava, UN Konvencija o pravima djeteta, klimatski sporovi mladih.